

Novel synthesis of β -lactams and their biological evaluation[†]

Bimal K. Banik

Department of Chemistry, The University of Texas-Pan American, 1201 West University Drive,
Edinburg, Texas 78539, USA

E-mail : bimalbanik10@gmail.com

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Abstract : Stereoselective synthesis of racemic and optically active novel β -lactams using Staudinger cycloaddition reaction with imines and ketenes has been achieved. Microwave induced-reactions have been performed for the preparation of these types of β -lactams and products derived from them. The formation of *trans*- β -lactams has been rationalized via isomerization of the enolates formed between the reactions of acid chloride (equivalent) with imines in the presence of a tertiary base. A donor-acceptor complex formation has been found to be the intermediate occurred in the formation of *cis*- β -lactams. A *peri* hydrogen in the aromatic rings has been proved to be crucial in controlling the isomer distribution of the products. Glycosylation reaction has been performed to prepare a few intermedeaites that are useful for anticancer agents. Cell-growth inhibition study has identified a few β -lactams that demonstrates anticancer activity. Microwave-induced reactions have been conducted for the synthesis of diverse heterocycles using β -lactams as the starting compounds.

Keywords : β -Lactams, Staudinger reaction, stereochemistry, mechanism of action, microwave-induced reactions, glycosylation, heterocycles, anticancer agents.

Introduction

Organic compounds have been used for the treatment of various medical disorders for the past several centuries although organic chemistry is not too old. In fact, the most commonly available drugs are all organic in nature. In the present generation, chemistry has become the central subject in science. Because of the most intense growth, chemistry has been divided into many sub-disciplines. Organic and medicinal chemistry have received most significant attention from the scientific community because of the application they can offer to our daily lives. Organic and medicinal chemistry of the β -lactam ring systems have numerous clinical applications. Considering the number of publications and patents in this area of β -lactam, one can argue that no other single area has resulted in so many exposures. On this basis, research on β -lactam rings has exploded and become very challenging. For example, penicillins, cephalosporins and many other antibiotics have targeted various biologically relevant enzymes¹. The practical use of crucial β -lactam

antibiotics and β -lactamase inhibitors has challenged scientists to prepare a variety of new and novel β -lactams². In addition to their independent use, β -lactams have also served as starting materials for the preparation of numerous heterocycles of biological significance³. The notable discovery has included the application of hydroxy β -lactams for the semi-synthesis of most popular anticancer drug, paclitaxel (Taxol) and docetaxel (Taxotere)⁴. The clinical applications of β -lactams as therapeutic agents for lowering cholesterol in blood have created a history⁵. Synthetic, biological and pharmacological studies of human leukocyte elastase inhibitory mechanisms of β -lactams have also been advanced⁶. Highly demanding processes, for example, catalytic asymmetric⁷ and polymer-supported⁸ synthesis of β -lactams have been identified. These results confirm that the synthesis and clinically useful antibacterial and therapeutically crucial β -lactams has become the central subject for many years and as a result, intense investigations have been pursued on this subject⁹⁻¹¹.

Our endeavor in β -lactams research is very diverse. A

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number of methods for the synthesis of new β -lactams¹² and biologically active compounds have been demonstrated by our group for the past several years^{13,14}. We have described stereoselective synthesis of novel anticancer β -lactams starting from polyaromatic imines. Although the chemistry of β -lactam as antibiotics is extremely rich and it has no parallel, however, studies of these molecules as anticancer agents have not been investigated until we have initiated an exploration in this area. Very recently, some scientists also have focused on the limited synthesis and studied the mechanism of action of anticancer β -lactams. Based on our independent work, we realize that β -lactams can be used as anticancer agents and these novel molecules may have acceptable toxicity but increased activity against cancer cells. This hypothesis has been tested and exciting results has been obtained.

Synthesis and biological evaluation of polycyclic aromatic compounds as antitumor agents is one of our research area. The open chain compounds obtained from polyaromatic imines and their good anticancer effects, we hypothesize that superior and less toxic β -lactams could be synthesized following of conformational constraint. Conformational ring constraint in our molecules can be achieved through a ring closure strategy. Structures **1** and **2** indicated that a ring closure reaction using N₁ and C₄ would form a more restricted β -lactam of structure **3** compared to the flexible compounds. On this basis, it has been envisioned that β -lactam **3** shown in Fig. 1 would serve as a conformationally restricted analogue of open-chain polycyclic aromatic compounds (**1** and **2**) that have shown anticancer activity against various cancer cell lines *in vitro* and also in animal model. The *in vitro* cell culture data on various open chain polycyclic amides against a number of cancer cell lines has extended the scope to apply this method to β -lactams. The principal aims are divided into several sections and these are described herein.

Since no β -lactams exists that have a polycyclic aromatic ring connected to the nitrogen or carbon of the ring, the first objective was to identify methods for the preparation of these types of novel molecules. The subsequent objectives were to study their mechanism of formation, test these derivatives and evaluate them against cancer cell lines; identify their effectiveness with respect to open chain diamides of similar structures; study their toxicity and related chemistry necessary for drug development.

Fig. 1

Several experiments verified that conformationally constrained molecules have better biological profiles when compared to the relatively flexible open-chain compounds^{15,16}. This principle has been used extensively in organic and medicinal chemistry. Some of the pertinent examples are described here. UAB-8, a conformationally constrained analogue of retinoic acid, has superior toxicological properties relative to the non-restricted compounds. Indoles of melatonin has demonstrated superiority of the *cis*-constrained isomer over *trans* in many ways. Phenalenes have proved to be promising restricted ligands for melatonins also. The discovery of conformationally restricted Taxol and Taxotere analogues has been realized. Conformationally restricted compounds that are better effective than the less-restricted but similar compounds include antibiotic linezolid and nicotine. It has been suggested that the restricted structures can bind to the receptor of the cell more effectively than the non-restricted molecules. Conformationally non-restricted compounds have much higher entropy and therefore, the time required to bind to the receptor of the cells (or the components of the cells) becomes much less than the restricted molecules. On the basis of these above hypotheses and background science, we have anticipated that conformationally constrained analogues of open chain diamides (**1** and **2**) may increase activity against cancer cell lines. In β -lactam chemistry, this kind of hypothesis has been examined and it is established that certain β -lactams are stronger in lowering cholesterol in human plasma compared to open-chain substrates⁵.

Preparation of starting compounds

Preparation of polycyclic aromatic amines and aldehydes are necessary for studying the β -lactam ring formation reaction through an imine²⁰. However, polyaromatic amines and polyaromatic nitro compounds are difficult to obtain commercially and therefore, it is important to prepare them in the laboratory. Nitro derivatives can be converted into amino derivatives through a reduction method. In this study polycyclic aromatic nitro compounds, particularly those of chrysene, phenanthrene, pyrene, and dibenzofluorene are necessary. Nitration of hydrocarbons with concentrated nitric acid in sulfuric acid is a widely used reaction for aromatic nitration. However, this method can also give multiple nitro products and oxidation of the aromatic systems because of the presence of many reactive sites. To overcome the limitations of the conventional nitrating agent, our research has culminated in a novel synthesis of polyaromatic nitro compounds from polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) using bismuth nitrate impregnated with clay¹⁷. Interestingly, this method is found to be regioselective. No oxidation of the aromatic rings is detected and the yields of the products are high. The procedure is simple and avoids the use of corrosive and strong acids for the aromatic nitration.

Several methods are known to prepare polyaromatic amines from polyaromatic nitro compounds. Catalytic hydrogenation, catalytic transfer hydrogenation and several new methods have been found compatible for the reduction of polyaromatic nitro compound to polyaromatic amine. However, many of these methods were not suitable with PAH derivatives. Indium-¹⁸ and samarium-mediated^{18,19} reduction methods offered good opportunities to achieve this target. Indium-induced reaction was performed in water in the presence of ammonium chloride and samarium-induced reaction elicited a product within a few minutes using ultrasound. The indium-induced method was performed in 10 g scale, Scheme 1). This method produced **5**, **7**, **9** and **11** from **4**, **6**, **8** and **10**

Scheme 1

respectively in excellent yield. Preparation of polyaromatic aldehydes, phenanthrene **13**, chrysene **15**, and dibenzofluorene **19**, was performed using a previously described method²⁰ from the respective hydrocarbons **15**, **8**, and **19**. Synthesis of dibenzofluorene hydrocarbon **19** was achieved following the reaction between **16** and **17** through alkylation and cyclodehydration method (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

This method involved in alkylation, cyclodehydration and aromatization in a single operation.

Synthesis of novel β -lactams with polyaromatic imines

Numerous methods have been investigated for the synthesis of β -lactams. However, Staudinger cycloaddition reaction has been extensively studied for the preparation of β -lactams. In fact, no other reactions are as widely used as this reaction in the chemistry of β -lactams. The Staudinger reaction is studied for the synthesis of monocyclic β -lactams as well (Scheme 3, for example, **22** and **23**)^{12c}. An imine **21**, a tertiary base (triethylamine), and acid chloride **20** (or equivalent) is required for this reaction. Imine is derived from aldehyde and primary amine through a dehydration reaction.

Scheme 3

The stereochemistry of β -lactam rings may change depending upon the conditions of the experiments (Scheme 4). In organic synthesis, conditions of an experiment have proved to be the key in controlling the stereochemistry of the products. The reaction of acyloxy, alkoxy, and nitrogen-containing acid chloride (equivalent) with diaryl imines in organic solvents produced mainly *cis*- β -

Scheme 4

lactams²¹. In contrast, reaction of polyaromatic imines (**21**, **23**, **25**, **27**, **29**, and **36**) with acetoxy, phenoxy, and phthalimido acid chloride in the presence of triethylamine and organic solvents at -78 °C to room temperature produced *trans*- β -lactams (**25**, **27**, **29**, **31**, **33**, and **36**). This observation is interesting and unprecedented in literature. According to the earlier results, *cis*- β -lactams were expected²¹. The *trans*-stereochemistry of the products was verified from the proton NMR data. The coupling constant of the C₃ and C₄ hydrogens in the *cis*-compounds (J 5–6 Hz) was higher than that of in the *trans*-products (J 1–2 Hz). The differences in the coupling constants values are highly prominent and these can confirm the stereochemistry of β -lactams. Although *trans*- β -lactams were obtained in the first few reactions, isomeric polyaromatic imines (**37**, **39**, and **41**) produced exclusively *cis*- β -lactams (**38**, **40**, and **42**) (Scheme 5). However, imine **43** derived from *trans*-cinnamaldehyde and 1-amino pyrene afforded *cis*- β -lactam **44** (Scheme 6). The controversial results are intriguing and deserve special attention to investigate this process with other substrates. In order to study the Staudinger reaction with other similar substrates, various naphthalenyl and anthracenyl imines were reacted. The results became highly complicated. For example, the 1-

Scheme 5

Scheme 6

substituted compounds derived from these bicyclic and tricyclic linear aromatic systems (**24** and **26**) produced the *trans*-isomers (**25** and **27**). Interestingly, the 2-substituted compounds from these aromatic systems (**45** and **48**) produced a mixture of *cis*- (**47** and **50**) and *trans*-compounds (**46** and **49**) in a ratio of 1 : 1 (Scheme 7). The results described with isomeric naphthalenyl- and

Scheme 7

anthracenyl-compounds were not known. Scientists have performed many reactions to control the diastereoselectivity of β -lactams formation reaction with thousands of imines. However, the use of isomeric compounds to control the diastereoselectivity of β -lactams has not been explored. The only difference between the structures of these compounds is the presence of a *peri* hydrogen close to the 1-substituted isomer (other physical parameters of

the isomeric compounds remain the same). The *peri* hydrogen in **24** and **26** is closer to the imine bond than it is in **45** and **48**. It is interesting to note that the 1-substituted isomers produced products like imines that have polyaromatic system at nitrogen. But, the results from the 2-substituted compounds did not follow any predictions. The ratio of the isomeric compounds with 2-substituted isomers can be changed with variations of the reaction conditions (temperature, solvents, etc.). In contrast, the 1-substituted imines produced only the *trans*-isomer regardless of the conditions of the experiments.

The synthesis of β -lactams following the Staudinger cycloaddition reaction of imine and ketene (or related species) was discovered more than hundred years ago and several scientists used this method in their beta lactam research. But, the formation of *trans*- β -lactams as reported herein with polyaromatic compounds had not been described in the literature^{12c}. However, a few studies were investigated toward the synthesis of *trans*- β -lactams following different reaction conditions. For example, synthesis of *trans*- β -lactams was achieved using microwave irradiation and changing the order of addition of the reagents²². In addition, *trans*- β -lactams were formed as the only products when cyclic imines were employed as the starting materials in the Staudinger cycloaddition. But, those cyclic imines were completely different in structures than the polyaromatic imines as described in this present work.

Microwave-induced synthesis of β -lactams

The use of domestic and automated microwave in chemistry is an active area of research for the past two decades²³. Microwave irradiation of a solution of imines **24**, **26** and **32** with acetoxyacetyl chloride in chlorobenzene using a domestic and automated microwave oven produced exclusively *trans*- β -lactams **25**, **27** and **33**, respectively (Scheme 8).

However, pure *cis*- β -lactams **47** and **50** did not isomerize to thermodynamically more stable *trans*- β -lactams **46** and **49** when irradiated separately in a microwave oven using chlorobenzene and triethylamine. These experiments clearly confirmed that there is no isomerization of the *cis*- β -lactams to the more stable *trans*- β -lactams during reaction of imines with acid chlorides at a high temperature and/or under microwave irradiation. This reaction

Scheme 8

was then extended with other similar substrates. Microwave irradiation of **24**, **26** and **32** with phenoxy acetyl chloride and benzyloxyacetyl chloride under identical conditions produced the *trans*-products as the only isomers within a few minutes instead of several days as required by the conventional method. Therefore, the present study clearly established that microwave irradiation with limited amounts of solvents can accelerate stereocontrolled synthesis of diverse β -lactams in a unique way²⁴. It was found that N-methylmorpholine is a better base than triethylamine when microwave irradiation condition is employed. Interestingly, no differences of yields of the products are observed in the domestic and automated microwave oven. Moreover, the yields of the products under conventional conditions and microwave irradiation method remain very similar. There are a number of advantages of using microwave irradiation. These include the followings but not limited to amounts of solvent (much less amount of solvent is required in the microwave method compared to conventional method), time of the reaction (the rate of reaction under microwave irradiation is significantly faster), simple glass apparatus (a beaker/Erlenmyer flask with a loose funnel is required in the domestic microwave-induced reaction. Higher activation energy transformations that are difficult and impossible to complete with conventional heating methods (oil bath, steam bath, and mantle) can be performed very expeditiously with microwave irradiation because of the facile energy transfer process among the reactants. Heat is applied externally and it passes through the walls of the reaction vessel and solvent during thermally-assisted chemical reactions. It is obvious that there is some loss of heat in this process. Therefore, some of the temperature-sensitive reactions may not prove efficient. However, microwave-induced reactions have numerous advantages

because the reactants receive activation due to microwave-coupling, microwave heating, microwave irradiation and molecular heating. A precise definition of these parameters is not possible. But, scientists have come up with an understanding how these work together and simultaneously accelerating the reaction rate lowering the activation energy. Microwave coupling is the direct transfer of microwave energy to a substrate that results in instantaneous heating. Microwave heating is the direct energy transfer process to the reaction mixtures; this raises kinetic excitation and is characterized by rapid energy transfer. Microwave irradiation is a form of non-ionizing radiation that transfers energy by interacting with polar molecules. In addition, the direct energy transfer from microwave to the molecules will greatly enhance the speed of the chemical reaction (solventless reaction).

Mechanism of β -lactam formation with polyaromatic imines

The mechanism of β -lactam formation through Staudinger cycloaddition reaction has been studied by many investigators. But, the rationale for the observed diastereoselectivity and enantioselectivity in many instances remains unclear and unproven. It has been demonstrated that the stereoselectivity of β -lactam formation depends on various parameters: the structures of the imine and acid-chloride (equivalent), order of addition of the reagents, nature of the solvent, temperature at the beginning and final stage of the reaction, nature of the bases, slow addition or fast addition of the reagents including the tertiary bases and many other conditions. In many examples, *cis*- β -lactam was found to be the exclusive or major product when acid chloride (equivalent) was added dropwise at low to room temperature to the solution of imine and a tertiary base. But, different stereoisomer was synthesized by changing the order of addition of the reagents. For example, a *trans*- β -lactam was the major or exclusive product when a tertiary base was slowly added to a dilute solution of imine and acid chloride (equivalent) solution at high temperature. This change of stereochemistry was highly successful with diarylimines. From a series of data, Georg and Ravikumar established a few general rules regarding stereoselectivity in the formation of β -lactam rings through Staudinger cycloaddition reaction²¹. The data presented by them was unique for numerous examples. However, despite high predictability,

it appeared the rules are not sufficient to follow the stereo-chemical origin in many new examples. Computer-assisted calculations were advanced to explain the stereochemical preferences in some specific examples^{25,26}. Cossio *et al.*²⁵ and Sordo *et al.*²⁶ explained the stereoselectivity of the products on the basis of important torquoelectronic effects. Low-temperature infrared spectroscopy was also used to identify the reactive intermediates and define the mechanism of the process²⁷. In general, two mechanisms were advanced to explain the product distribution in the β -lactam formation reaction. The ketene mechanism was observed in a low temperature infrared spectroscopy study of acid chloride-imine reaction²⁷ while the acylation of imine mechanism was believed to be involved in some examples²¹. These mechanisms were supported by numerous evidences. It had been hypothesized that cycloaddition reaction of the imine occurred from the least hindered side of the ketene and this process generated zwitterionic intermediate and subsequent conrotatory cyclization of these intermediates then produced *cis*- and *trans*- β -lactams in varying proportions. Acylation reaction of the imine by the acid chloride in the presence of a tertiary base to form N-acyliminium chloride also produced zwitterionic intermediates.

The cinnamyl or polyaromatic system at C₄ may exerted more effects than the contribution of the N-polyaromatic system, resulting in *cis*- β -lactam formation. Subsequent proton abstraction from complex lead to *cis*- β -lactam through 90° bond rotation and closure or anion inversion and closure through an usual procedure. This hypothesis was further strengthened by the possible formation of donor-acceptor complex suggested by Bose *et al.*³⁰. This complex formation effectively stabilized the transition state of the reaction leading to *cis*- β -lactam formation. In another study, Cossio *et al.*^{25a} described that the S_N2 intramolecular mechanism favored the preferential or exclusive formation of *trans*- β -lactams, when the reactions were allowed to take place in the absence of a tertiary base in the initial stages of the reaction. Although in some examples, yields of the products was increased using a higher boiling tertiary base, the use of diisopropylethyl amine as the base could not improve the yield of products with polyaromatic compounds. However, the stereochemistry of the products remained identical as that was obtained with triethylamine. Lassaletta

*et al.*³¹ explained the diastereoselectivity of *trans*- β -lactam formation following steric reasons. It had been postulated that the isomerization of the imine bond was involved prior to ring closure as a result of severe steric interactions between N-benzyloxycarbonyl-N-benzylamnio group and the alkyl group of hydrazone. This mechanism explained *trans*-selectivity of some products, but could not explain the formation of *cis*-isomers with similar types of compounds. Importantly, the formation of a mixture of *cis*- and *trans*-isomers with naphthalenyl and anthracenyl imines could not be explained using any of the mechanisms described above²⁵⁻³¹. If the electron withdrawal properties or the steric crowding of the N-Polyaromatic systems were mainly responsible for the *trans*- β -lactam formation, an identical stereochemical distribution of the products would have been observed in the isomeric naphthalenyl and anthracenyl compounds. N-Polyaromatic systems produced *trans*-isomers as the only products and they revealed a structural similarity. Imines that have a *peri* hydrogen very close to the C=N bond, whereas this *peri* hydrogen is relatively away from the same bond in imines that do not have these types of hydrogens. It appeared stabilization of the positive charge by the extended conjugation is the principal contributor in dictating the stereochemistry of the final β -lactams. These results also suggested that it is the nature of the C₄ group that controls the isomeric distribution of the products even with polyaromatic systems.

Anticancer activities of the β -lactams

Some of these β -lactams were tested using nine human cancer cell lines with cisplatin and diamide **1b** as controls. The results are shown in Table 1. The structure-activity study suggested that regardless of the configuration of the β -lactams, neither naphthalene and anthracene nor pyrene derivatives showed activity against

any of these cancer cell lines. Their maximum activity was determined to be at concentrations much higher concentration 20 μ M/mL. The *trans*-acetoxy phenanthrene and chrysene derivatives demonstrated reasonable activity. Phenoxy and phthalimido β -lactams were inactive. Interestingly, on the breast cancer cell line MCF-7, three compounds had identical activity, while on the colon cancer cell line HT-29, one compound was three times as active as cisplatin. Differences in cytotoxicity were also confirmed on the ovarian cancer cell line OVCAR, where cisplatin and another compound had equal activity. This selectivity of cytotoxicity differences among compounds was very striking.

All of the in vitro cytotoxicity assays were performed using MTT assay :

A number of conclusions can be made from the results of the *in vitro* studies. It was clear that the minimal structural requirement of the aromatic system for cytotoxicity is at least three aromatic rings in an angular configuration. This was confirmed by the fact that only phenanthrene **29a** and two chrysene derivatives **33a** and **33d** demonstrate cytotoxicity against the tumor cell lines. The other polyaromatic compounds derived from naphthalenes, anthracenes, and pyrene compounds were inactive. Interestingly, the presence of the acetoxy group proved to be very crucial for anticancer activity. Acetoxy is a well-established leaving group for reactions with a wide range of nucleophiles. This indicated that an enzymatic or other modification at this site is involved in the activation of these acetoxy compounds. It was very important to note that only the *trans*- β -lactams only have antitumor activity. Our study supports that certain conformationally restricted compounds, indeed, can demonstrate better activity in biological systems. It has been confirmed that *trans*- β -lactams are more active than diamide **1b** in many cancer cell lines *in vitro*.

Table 1. *In vitro* cytotoxicity of β -lactams on human cancer cell lines (μ M)

Compounds	BRO	MCF-7	MDA-231	OVCAR	SKOV	PC-3	HL-60	K-562	HT-29
Cisplatin	7.66	10.05	12.33	3.99	5.99	4.66	1.66	2.33	16.99
1b	33.64	40.0	12.23	18.11	11.05	27.29	9.41	12.70	16.70
29a	10.48	10.09	12.49	18.0	18.00	9.3	5.21	4.0	10.49
33a	10.84	9.81	11.98	4.17	6.88	16.32	3.64	4.33	5.66
33d	11.00	14.93	14.46	-	9.0	-	2.5	2.5	15.90
All others	>20	>20	>20	>20	>20	>20	>20	>20	>20

Asymmetric synthesis of anticancer β -lactam

It is known that an optically active isomer of a racemic compound has better and much selective biological activity. Tremendous success has been achieved in the cycloaddition of optically active aminoketene with imines. In contrast, the analogous reaction of imines with chiral hydroxyketene equivalents has not been explored systematically. The reaction of achiral alkoxy ketenes with chiral imines derived from optically active α -oxy and α -amino carbonyl compounds had been investigated for the preparation of optically active β -lactams. Asymmetric synthesis of *cis*-hydroxy β -lactam (70% yield) derived from α -O-glycoside as the ketene component was reported with diaryl imine. The control of absolute stereochemistry was the most challenging part. The stereochemistry of the anomeric center of the carbohydrate is very crucial. Our hypothesis was to use the glycosides (α - and β -) as the ketene component. We predicted that the absolute stereochemistry of the anomeric center in the ketene component of the carbohydrate would be the most important although the nature of the other center with different protective groups may play an important role in the formation of the β -lactam ring. Ferrier rearrangement was used for the preparation of the starting β -glycosides. Reaction of 3,4,5-tri-O-acetyl D-glucal (**51**) with benzyl glycolate (**52**) in the presence of iodine has produced a glycoside **53**. Hydrogenolysis of the benzyl ester **53** and the hydrogenation of the alkene group had been performed by catalytic hydrogenation to afford acid **54** (Scheme 9).

Scheme 9

Reaction of the activated acid **54** with polyaromatic imine **56** in the presence of triethylamine produced a mixture of diastereomeric O-glycosides of *trans*- β -lactams **58** and **59** in a ratio of 45 : 55. The diastereomers **58** and **59** were separated through column chromatography. Acid-mediated reaction was used to cleave the anomeric bond and this process produced *trans*-hydroxy β -lactams (+)-**60** and (-)-**62** in excellent yield. The hydroxy compounds were converted to the acetates (+)-**61** and (-)-**63** (Scheme

Scheme 10

10). The absolute stereochemistry of the *trans*-acetoxy- β -lactam (+)-**61** and (-)-**63** was confirmed by comparison with known *trans*- β -lactam described earlier³². An application of this chemistry was extended to a similar reaction with a β -glycoside. The synthesis of the acid with a β -glycoside bond was performed. Indium-induced reaction of acetobromoglucose (**64**) with **65** afforded an ester **66**. Hydrogenolysis of the benzyl group produced the β -glycoside **67** (Scheme 11).

Scheme 11

Cycloaddition of the acid **67** with imine **56** was performed in the presence of N-methyl-2-chloropyridinium iodide (**57**) and triethylamine. NMR analyses of the crude reaction mixture showed the presence of two diastereomeric *trans*- β -lactams **69** and **70** in 60 : 40 ratios. The diastereomeric O-glycosides after separation was treated with mild aqueous acid to the hydroxy compounds **60** and **62** and the resulting alcohols were converted to acetates. The absolute stereochemistry of the *trans*-acetoxy- β -lactam **61** and **63** was confirmed by a comparison with known *trans*- β -lactam as described earlier and above (Scheme 12).

In vitro cytotoxicity of the optically active β -lactams :

These optically active β -lactams were tested using seven human cancer cell lines against cisplatin and racemic β -lactam as controls.

The cell growth inhibition data confirmed that of the optically active β -lactam **61** was extremely active (obtained from two different pathways) and the activity of the other optical isomer **63** (obtained from two different pathways) was reduced compared to the racemic β -lactam **33a** (Table 2).

Mechanism of action

Because of the presence of the cyclic four-membered amide connected to the multicyclic ring systems, an effort to define their mechanism of action would be highly important. Despite a number of synthetic efforts, a relatively small amount of research had been focused on the use of compounds related to PAHs as anticancer agents. Bair *et al.*³³ reported a close correlation between antitumor activity and the shape of the polyaromatic system. However, his group did not make a definitive correlation between the ability of these compounds to bind to DNA

and their cytotoxic activity. Bair's group developed benzylic aminopropanediols from structure-activity studies. These amino propanediols were believed to interact with DNA via intercalation and to be topoisomerase II inhibitors. The antitumor activity of two of the most active naphthalimides, amonafide and mitonafide had been established due to intercalation to DNA. To improve its potency, naphthalene was modified to anthracene to serve as the chromophore. The resulting compound, azonafide showed increased cytotoxic activity over naphthalene-based analogues. Not all azonafide derivatives, which had characteristic mechanistic properties when compared with existing classes of DNA intercalators, were localized in the nucleus. Other differences with existing DNA intercalators, such as mitoxantrone had included a lack of inhibition of topoisomerase II enzymes at equicytotoxic concentrations. Improving cellular cytotoxic potency was adopted by linking two naphthalimide or anthralimide groups with a polyamine bridge. The mechanism of action of β -lactams as different types of biologically active compounds had been studied. However, investigations directed to define the mechanism of action of β -lactams as anticancer agents had not been explored. The active compounds may follow one of these mechanisms as described above or it may act on cancer cells through a novel mechanism.

Mutagenicity assays

Mutagenicity assays were performed by BioReliance Corporation as study AA65FL-FM.501.BTA. Compounds **29a** and **33a** were examined using the Salmonella Plate Incorporation, Mutagenicity Assay. The tester strains used were Salmonella typhimurium histidine auxotrophs TA98 and TA100^{14b}. Tester strain TA98 was reverted from auxotrophy to prototrophy by frame shift mutagens. Tester strain TA100 was reverted by mutagens that cause both frame shift and base pair substitution mutations. Both of these compounds were exposed separately via the plate

Table 2. *In vitro* cytotoxicity of optically active β -lactams on human cancer cell Lines (μ M)

Compounds	BRO	MDA-231	SKOV-3	PC-3	HL-60	K-562	HT-29
Cisplatin	7.66	12.33	5.99	4.66	1.66	2.33	16.99
Racemic 33a	15.7	8.7	10.00	11.1	0.7	1.1	2.0
(+)- 61	6.1	0.8	6.8	1.4	0.7	1.1	0.7
(-)- 63	22.0	8.5	6.1	15.5	5.4	6.0	8.3

incorporation methodology. Each one of the β -lactam was tested at ten dose levels along with appropriate vehicle control and positive controls with tester strains TA98 and TA100 in the presence and absence of Aroclor-induced rat liver S9. All dose levels of test compounds, vehicle control and positive controls, were plated in duplicate. For each compound to be evaluated positive, it must have demonstrated a dose-related increase in the mean revertants per plate for at least one tester strain over a minimum of two increasing concentrations of the test article. Data sets for tester strains TA98 and TA100 were judged to be positive if the increase in mean revertants at the peak of the dose response was equal to or greater than twice the mean vehicle control value. The results of the mutagenicity assay indicated that neither **29a** nor **33a** demonstrated a positive response with these tester strains at any concentration in either the presence or absence of Aroclor-induced rat liver S9, indicating that neither of these compounds demonstrate any mutagenicity. This is an important finding in the field of cancer research.

Apoptosis

To determine whether exposure to **29a** and/or **33a** induced DNA cleavage in sensitive and/or resistant tumor cell lines, the APO-BRDU assay was performed. Compound **33a** demonstrated no significant increase in BRDU insertion into the DNA of HL-60 cells exposed for 24 h. In two identical runs **29a** also failed to demonstrate an increase in BRDU insertion. These results were striking since in all of these experiments, concentrations approximately twice that required for the IC_{50} of **29a** and three times greater than that for **33a** were used. In one of these experiments, MDA-231, a human breast cancer line that was resistant *in vitro* to the effects of **33a**, was tested for BRDU insertion. As expected from the above experiments, a significant increase was not detected. These results confirmed scanning electron microscopy studies of exposed cells that suggested the lack of alterations in these cancer cell lines, which were associated with the induction of apoptosis in the target cancer cells.

Interactions with topoisomerases

TOPOGEN, Inc. has the necessary kits to identify the interaction of organic compounds with topoisomerases. These kits contained reagents required for detection of topoisomerase I and II with DNA markers for detection

of enzymatic action and standard topoisomerase inhibitors. The activity of **29a** and **33a** was determined using these systems. No inhibition of either topoisomerase I or topoisomerase II was detected in the HL-60 cancer cell lines using much higher concentration that were required to inhibit the growth of this cell lines *in vitro*. Therefore, there was no evidence that the active β -lactams had their cytotoxic activity in sensitive cell lines through interaction with DNA or DNA-associated enzyme systems. These compounds failed to increase BRDU insertion into DNA and display inhibitory action toward the two topoisomerase systems. The failure to induce apoptosis was consistent with these findings because in many instances, this phenomenon was the putative result of such DNA interactions.

Cell cycle activity

Cell cycle activity of the active compounds was investigated. Propidium iodine (the marker for DNA content) was used as a marker of the cell cycle. This cytometric determination was calibrated separately and calculated for a related program to evaluate the percentage of cells in each phase of the cell cycle. The treated cells were compared with that of control HL-60 cancer cells for the percentage of cells in each cell cycle compartment over a period of 24 h. HL-60 cells treated with 10 μ g of **33a** demonstrated an increase in the percentage of cells in the G_2 phase that was particularly predominating at 24 h. The average percentage of untreated cells in G_2 was 17.2%, and that of cells treated with **33a** and **29a** was 38.4% and 23.6%, respectively. To determine whether alteration of the cell cycle occurred in a cell line that had repeatedly demonstrated resistance to the *in vitro* effect of **33a**, the human breast cancer cell line MDA-231 was examined. HL-60 cells treated with **33a** (1 μ g) demonstrated a striking increase at 24 h (34.1%), but no increase was detected in MDA-231, which was identical to that in untreated MDA-231 cells (approximately 14%)^{14b}.

Microwave-induced environmentally benign synthetic procedure

During the course of our investigations on the synthesis of β -lactams, polyaromatic compounds, steroids and other heterocycles we have found it convenient to perform several types of synthetic steps using microwave

irradiation. 'Microwave-Induced Organic Reaction Enhancement (MORE)' chemistry techniques have been demonstrated for nontraditional methods for rapid, safe and environmentally friendly methods. These reactions are conducted in unmodified domestic microwave ovens in a matter of minutes using very limited amounts of high boiling solvents (such as DMF, ethylene dichloride and ethylene glycol) or in the absence of solvents if one of the reactants is a suitable liquid. Clearly, this method has received spectacular attention from scientists as can be proved by several thousands of published papers in various journals.

Domestic microwave ovens generate radiation of 2450 MHz frequency which is directed into the inner cavity of the oven. The level of the microwave energy can be controlled by an on-off cycle that can be manipulated for various levels of low or high energy. Therefore, selective microwave energy can be transferred to the reactants directly. Microwaves are non-ionizing radiation with dipoles. Glass, ceramic materials and many polymeric materials are transparent to microwaves and therefore, they do not absorb microwave energy. Significant advantage is taken of this crucial property of microwaves to adequately reduce the amount of organic solvents needed as the medium or microwave energy transfer agent. Upon irradiating a reaction mixture containing all the reactants together in an open glass vessel depending upon the scale of the experiment (a large beaker or Erlenmyer flask with a loose cover), microwave irradiation is transferred to the reactants directly without heating the glass vessel and extraction container. The energy generated by the microwave oven is controlled precisely so that the solvent and/or the reaction mixtures are not allowed to boil and the flask is removed from the microwave oven without any trouble. This method limits the amount of vaporization significantly, if not completely and therefore, no reflux condenser is essential. The large container can condense the vapor if there is extra heating. Magnetic stirrers are not required if the reaction mixture is placed as a thin layer (like silica gel over a glass plate) in the glass vessel used so that microwave radiation can penetrate into the entire reaction mixture very efficiently. The usual reaction time is a few minutes even on a few hundred grams scale depending upon the nature of the reactions. However, an optimization of the reaction condition is required

since it has been found that the time may differ significantly depending upon the size and nature of the microwave oven, on-off cycle, solvent, size of the reaction vessel and heat sink. Since the reaction is very fast, a variation of one of these parameters may cause acceleration or retardation of reaction rate as well as the stereochemistry of the products.

Although microwave-induced reactions have been studied extensively, the role of this energy in organic synthesis is not understood properly. It is not established whether microwaves change the transition state parameters of reactions through rapid supply of energy to the reaction mixture. Some evidences support that the radiation is responsible for accelerated rate of the chemical reactions. Many others believe that microwave radiation has no effects on chemical reactions : it serves simply like a heating instrument. But, many laboratories including our own have reported that microwave-induced reactions are much faster, high yielding, comparatively free of by-products and sometimes can direct the stereochemistry of the products. A major superiority of MORE process method is the minimum amount of solvents used. Slurries of the reactants at room temperature are adequate and allow enough reactants to go into solution at the high temperatures reached very rapidly in a microwave oven in 1 or 2 min. This process facilitates the reaction rate dramatically. Much reduction in the use of solvents as reaction media and clean reaction with better stereochemistry control, reduce pollution at the source and ensure high levels of efficiency from a practical point of view. Another advantage of MORE chemistry process is the lowered energy consumption compared to conventional heating under reflux. The use of high boiling polar solvent adds significant value to the microwave-induced reactions. The reaction mixture under irradiation is not allowed to come to the boiling point so there is minimum vaporization. Also, microwave-assisted reactions on several hundred grams scale-require only 10-15 min of irradiation in a domestic microwave oven of 800-1000 W power. Commercial microwave ovens are available for kilogram scale preparative reactions. The availability of such equipment certainly adds significant use of MORE chemistry techniques for chemical development research. On this basis, microwave-enhanced chemical synthesis has played an important role for the manufacture of spe-

cialty pharmaceuticals such as peptides, β -lactam, heterocycles, steroids, alkaloids, and their analogs.

Catalytic transfer hydrogenation in β -lactam chemistry

A few laboratories have employed catalytic transfer hydrogenation (CTH) in their research³³. This is a safe and efficient operation in which a catalyst and hydrogen gas are replaced with a catalyst and a hydrogen donor such as cyclohexene, hydrazine, formic acid, sodium formate, ammonium formate, cyclohexadiene, and phosphinic acid, sodium hypophosphite. Ethyl alcohol is a common solvent for CTH. However, catalytic transfer hydrogenation can be conducted very rapidly and in quantitative yield inside an unmodified domestic microwave oven in ethylene glycol. The β -lactam underwent selective hydrogenolysis of the O-benzyl group and reduction of the unsaturated ester group to a saturated ester side chain to yield the β -lactam which retained the N-benzyl group intact when 10% Pd/C was used as the catalyst following this method. This reaction demonstrates selectivity of hydrogenation reactions.

Ojima *et al.* demonstrated a cleavage of N-C₄ bonds in 4-phenyl-2-azetidinones to prepare phenylalanine derivatives in high yield³⁴. This reaction was conducted using catalytic hydrogenation method (ambient pressure of hydrogen at 50°C in methanol with Pd/C as the catalyst). In the presence of an excess of Raney nickel catalyst and hydrogen, 3-methoxy-1,4-diphenyl-2-azetidinone underwent β -lactam cleavage and a very small amount of the anilide of α -methoxy- β -phenylpropionic acid was obtained. But, cleavage of the β -lactam ring did not occur under mild conditions. However, additional investigation on this reaction was very crucial in obtaining unknown results. Microwave-mediated catalytic transfer hydrogenolysis was investigated. This reaction was conducted at 110–120 °C using 10% Pd/C as the catalyst. In every instance, extremely fast scission of 4-phenyl-2-azetidinones was noted in the presence of ammonium formate and sodium formate as the hydrogen donor. The N-benzyl group of the β -lactam ring under this condition was not removed. But, the O-benzyl group at C-3 was removed and converted to an alcoholic OH group; unsaturated β -lactams were reduced to alkyl β -lactams. The reduction product was obtained in high yield and very rapidly. Ra-Ni did

not cause cleavage of the β -lactam ring under these conditions.

Enantiospecific synthesis of (-)-2S,3S-2-amino-3,4-dihydroxybutyric acid

Suitably substituted β -lactams are used for the synthesis of optically pure polyhydroxy amino acid with multiple chiral centers. Microwave-induced reactions was used in many of these steps in the preparation of these types of molecules³⁵. The 3-hydroxy-2-azetidinones were the starting materials to obtain polyhydroxy amino acids. Commercially available D-mannitol derivative was selected as one of the starting compounds. D-Mannitol was manipulated in different ways for the preparation of polyhydroxy amino acids. An unusual amino acid was prepared. L- γ -Hydroxythreonin received much attention. Klenk and Diebold observed that this molecule is one of the oxidative products of shingosine. Therefore, numerous syntheses of this compound were published. The starting material for this synthesis was D-glyceraldehyde acetonide which react with benzyl amine to form an optically active imine. Reaction of this imine with benzyloxyacetyl chloride and triethylamine using microwave irradiation produced a *cis*- β -lactam stereospecifically with known absolute configuration.

Microwave-induced catalytic transfer hydrogenation was performed at approximately 110 °C with ammonium formate or sodium formate as the hydrogen donor and 10% Pd/C as the catalyst³³. This reaction had important implications. For example, selective hydrogenolysis was observed : the benzyloxy group was converted to a hydroxy group through hydrogenolysis but the N-benzyl group was remained intact. Lithium aluminum hydride-mediated reaction cleaved the β -lactam ring and produced a vicinal diol system. Oxidation of this diol failed to yield the desired acid. This reaction proved to be problematic because of the presence of the amino group. A protection of the amino group with electron withdrawing group was necessary prior conducting the oxidation reaction of the diol. Microwave-induced catalytic transfer hydrogenation was successful to remove the N-benzyl group to afford the primary amino alcohol. The amino group was protected with a t-butoxycarbonyl group using known method. The ultimate goal was to prepare an L-amino acid. Consequently, the diol used and an acid was prepared by

ruthenium tetraoxide oxidation of the unprotected diol. The amino acid derivative obtained was reacted with trifluoroacetic acid to remove the ketal and Boc groups. The levorotatory or the natural form of β -hydroxy threonine was obtained. Our attention was turned to prepare a different polyhydroxy amino acid, polyoxamic acid. This polyhydroxyamino acid and its mirror image isomer were the target of synthesis in several laboratories due to their medicinal activities³⁷. At the first step, imine was obtained through a condensation of with benzyl amine and aldehyde with multiple chiral centers and it was allowed to react with benzyloxyacetyl chloride and triethylamine, under microwave irradiation and a single optically active β -lactam was the product. The absolute configuration of the chiral center next to the aldehyde group was the determining factor to assign the absolute configuration of this *cis*- β -lactam. Optically active (–)-polyoxamic acid was then prepared through a series of steps. During the course of this work several protections/deprotections reactions were investigated.

Stereoselectivity of α -vinyl β -lactams formation reaction

Vinyl β -lactams are crucial starting compounds for the synthesis of different types of heterocycles. These compounds are synthesized using microwave irradiation. A straightforward synthesis of α -vinyl- β -lactams by the reaction of α,β -unsaturated acid chloride (e.g. *trans*-crotonyl chloride) with imine in the presence of triethylamine in refluxing dichloromethane or benzene was realized^{20b}. Exclusive formation of *trans*- β -lactams was noted from *trans*-crotonyl chloride and the diaryl imine. Zamboni and Just used this method for the synthesis of many *trans*- α -vinyl- β -lactams as important intermediates for β -lactam antibiotics³⁹. Similarly, the reaction of dimethylacryloyl chloride and the imine to obtain the *trans*- β -lactam was made available. Crotonyl chloride and dimethylacryloyl chloride worked similarly in the formation of α -vinyl- β -lactams. In some instances, the products are *trans*- β -lactams. However, in some examples, formation of *cis*-isomers was also observed. At room temperature the *cis*-isomer was formed predominantly but at higher temperature the *trans*-product was the major isomer. Imine obtained from aliphatic amine produced the *cis*- α -vinyl- β -lactam as the major isomer. Imines from aromatic aldehydes and substituted anilines in general produced only

trans- α -vinyl- β -lactams. In contrast, imine from benzaldehyde and methylamine produced a mixture of *cis*- and *trans*- β -lactams in a ratio depending upon the temperature of the reaction mixture and other parameters of the reaction. Higher temperature favored the formation of the *trans*- β -lactam through a thermodynamically-controlled process. However, this reaction was not a base-catalyzed isomerization. *cis*- β -Lactam did not produce *trans*- β -lactam and was recovered after irradiation in the presence of N-methylmorpholine. The formation of the *cis*- β -lactam was higher initially. But, as the reaction proceeded the profile was changed. After 10 min of microwave irradiation, *trans*- β -lactam was formed as the predominant isomer in many examples. It was necessary to keep water as the heat sink in the microwave oven to control the temperature of the reaction mixtures. Water absorbed a portion of microwave heat and prevented reactants not to evaporate. Importantly, *cis*- β -lactams were obtained as the only products from acid chlorides or and imine (obtained from glyoxalic ester or phenyl glyoxal) regardless of the temperature of the reaction. The reason for the formation of *cis*- β -lactams from glyoxalic ester and phenyl glyoxal under microwave irradiation remained unexplained. However, the presence of an electron-withdrawing group at the C-4 position could be important in the formation of *cis*- β -lactams. Isomerization as obtained in this study required purification of the products. However, isomerization of β -lactam formation could be avoided starting from a different compound. For example, the *cis/trans*-isomerism was not possible when an imine derived from a ketomalonnate was used for the preparation of the vinyl- β -lactam. But, an isomer was also produced in which the alkene group in the side chain is conjugated with the β -lactam carbonyl group³⁶. This reaction was used with other substrates using different groups at nitrogen of the β -lactam ring. Dealkoxycarbonylation of β -lactams was performed using lithium chloride in DMF. Microwave irradiation of the C-4 diester produced a mixture of E and Z isomers in almost equal amounts. Conjugation of the alkene group with carbonyl group of the amide was possible during microwave irradiation. The mixture of unsaturated compounds was then reduced to the saturated compounds by microwave-assisted catalytic transfer hydrogenation. The stereochemistry of the products from this study was found to be exclusively *cis* as expected.

Synthesis of these types of alkyl-substituted β -lactam was very difficult through direct Sadunger cycloaddition of saturated acid chloride with imine in the presence of a tertiary base.

Glycosylation of alcohols

We developed bismuth nitrate pentahydrate-catalyzed reactions. Nitration of aromatic hydrocarbons, phenolic compounds and the aromatic group in β -lactams were performed in excellent yield. These reactions were very important because phenolic compounds and β -lactams were functionalized using bismuth nitrate at high temperature. No oxidation of phenol and cleavage of β -lactam rings were observed even through reaction temperature were high. A remarkable Michael reaction of indoles and carbamates with unsaturated ketones was also conducted with bismuth nitrate³⁷. The mechanism of these bismuth nitrate-catalyzed reactions was not explored. However, a coordination of the bismuth with the carbonyl group was speculated. There were numerous advantages of using bismuth salts; high catalytic activity, the non-toxicity, cost and mildness were the principal features. Interestingly, bismuth nitrate and bismuth triflate proved to be effective in catalyzing a Ferrier rearrangement³⁸.

Reaction of alcohols with 3,4,5-tri-O-acetyl D-glucal in the presence of bismuth nitrate or bismuth triflate (10–30 mol%) produced a single glycoside in 68–75% yield³⁹. The anomeric stereochemistry of these glycosides was determined as α -form the NMR coupling constant of the anomeric hydrogen (1–2 Hz) of a reduced isomer prepared by a catalytic hydrogenation experiment. The β -glycoside would have a higher coupling constant because of axial-axial interactions. This suggests that the nucleophile attacked the anomeric center exclusively from one face only. We used iodine in organic synthesis⁴⁰. In an extension of iodine-catalyzed glycosylation of alcohol (or bismuth salts-catalyzed reaction), we investigated chiral resolution of a racemic β -lactam alcohol that is present in thienamycin antibiotic side chain for obtaining both enantiomers⁴¹. The aim was to prepare two diastereomeric O-glycosides by the Ferrier rearrangement as one of the key steps⁴⁴. More than 30 years ago, the clinical use of the antibiotic thienamycin was started. PS-5 and carptimycin also belonged to this family of antibiotics and have similar structures. In general, enantiomers

differ in their medicinal properties and therefore, availability of both enantiomeric forms of this compound is crucial⁴². It appeared that the sugar system in the glycosides exerted steric hindrance to the hydrogenolysis of the N_1 - C_4 bond. However, hydrogenation reaction for a long period of time afforded many uncharacterized materials. In the reaction mixtures several compounds were noted, these compounds were formed because of the cleavage of the N_1 - C_4 bond, reduction of the olefinic group and allylic deacetoxylation. The ¹H NMR spectra of the 2,3-dideoxy carbohydrate compound showed only small couplings for the anomeric hydrogen indicating an axial stereochemistry of the glycoside bonds. A higher coupling constant was expected with a β -glycoside product. Reaction with benzyl-protected glycal failed to produce any glycoside with the β -lactam alcohol. This confirmed earlier observation that the leaving group properties are crucial in this type of reaction. Glycal that was prepared from galactal with identical protective group did not yield the product. The two diastereomeric products were separated by column chromatography. Prolonged exposure of the crude products to silica gel caused decomposition. After separation, the sugar group was removed by aqueous hydrochloric acid. The cleavage reaction was also performed using bismuth nitrate under microwave irradiation to afford two enantiomeric alcohols. β -Lactam alcohols were converted into their acetates using standard method. The acetates were found to be enantiomerically pure as confirmed by ¹H NMR spectroscopy in the presence of an optically active shift reagent⁴³.

Stereoselectivity in the β -lactam formation reaction

The stereochemistry (*cis* and *trans*) of the β -lactams formed by the reaction of acid chloride and imine in the microwave oven with irradiation for a short period of time (1–2 min) at low power setting was almost identical as obtained by the traditional method. Our studies confirmed that it is possible to control the stereochemistry of β -lactam formation using high level microwave irradiation in a domestic microwave oven. For a study of the effect of microwave irradiation on the formation of hydroxy- β -lactams, several imines and the high boiling tertiary amine, N-methylmorpholine in place of lower boiling triethylamine were selected. Chlorobenzene was chosen as the reaction medium which absorbs microwave

energy because of high dipole moment. Experiments on the preparation of α -benzyloxy- β -lactams from benzyloxyacetyl chloride and N-methylmorpholine demonstrated the formation of varying amounts of *cis*- and *trans*- β -lactams. These results were interesting because this reaction should give only the *cis*-isomer in accordance with the previous results. It was observed that *cis*- β -lactam formation was the main pathways by lower power of microwave irradiation (power level 4–5). At about 112 °C reaction temperature, there was more *trans*-product than the *cis*-isomer. The reaction of the same acid chloride with imine derived from optically active D-glyceraldehyde acetonide was conducted under MORE chemistry conditions, only the *cis*- β -lactam was obtained both at low and high power settings. Different way to obtain *trans*-isomer was attempted. However, the product remained *cis*. Various attempts in the presence of a base were used to obtain *trans*- β -lactam with. However, all attempts failed : only a single *cis*- β -lactam was obtained. We investigated the β -lactam forming reaction when the imine was derived from an aromatic aldehyde and an aryl alkyl amine. When the cycloaddition was conducted in the traditional manner at 0 °C by the “normal addition” method, only the *cis*- β -lactam was formed. However, if the “inverse addition” method was used, 30% *cis*- and 70% *trans*- β -lactams were obtained under the same conditions in excellent yield. Therefore, the order of addition of reagents had a tremendous role on the stereochemistry of the β -lactam formation reaction through cycloaddition method. This suggests different mechanistic routes are possible to obtain different β -lactams by changing the order of addition of reagents. Interestingly, when this reaction was conducted in a microwave oven using chlorobenzene (preheated to about 110 °C) as the reaction medium, the ratio of *trans*- to *cis*- β -lactam was 90 : 10 irrespective of the sequence of addition (i.e. “normal addition” or “inverse addition”). It is difficult to explain these results. However, we hypothesized that fast reactions and additions were unable to differentiate the sequence of addition of the reagents. When the *cis*- β -lactam was heated with N-methylmorpholine in chlorobenzene solution for 30 min, there was no isomerization to the thermodynamically more stable *trans*- β -lactam. This study confirmed that the formation of *cis*- and *trans*- β -lactams followed multiple mechanisms. The transition state struc-

tures were altered by minor variation of the conditions of the experiments. Microwave irradiation seems to be responsible for the alteration of the transition state structures. β -Lactam ring was used as the starting compound for the preparation of anticancer drug. A compound of particular interest was the *cis*- β -lactam (and its *trans*-isomer) which was used as intermediates for the side chain of Taxol and its analogs such as Taxotere. Coupling with baccatin and chemical manipulation of the structures provided Taxol and Taxotere. When this cycloaddition reaction was conducted under microwave irradiation for 5 min, the ratio of the *trans*- to *cis*-isomer was 95 : 5. It was reported the preparation of the racemic form of the *trans*- β -lactam by the slow addition of triethylamine to a refluxing solution of the imine and the acid chloride in toluene solution²⁸. This *trans*- β -lactam is an intermediate for 2'-*epi*-taxol. From the results obtained above, it is concluded that the cycloaddition reaction involves multiple pathways some of which are highly accelerated and significant by rapid microwave irradiation. Higher temperature also facilitates *trans*- β -lactam formation. However, microwave irradiation is much more effective in the formation of specific *trans*- β -lactams. However, in the case of azetidinones formation, reactions were initially performed in refluxing toluene as the solvent. This was in an attempt to achieve β -lactam ring formation with *trans*-selectivity⁴⁴. The products were obtained diastereoselectively as pairs of isomers with the desired *trans*-C-3 and C-4-configuration, i.e. (3R,4S) and (3S,4R).

Tetrachlorophthaloyl glycine was prepared in 94% yield in 90 s in an unmodified domestic microwave oven. Protection of glycine on a molecular scale of commercially available tetrachlorophthalic anhydride was performed. Tetrachlorophthaloyl (TCP)-protected glycine was found to be isolated in more than 90% yield after 8 min of irradiation followed by crystallization of the crude material from methanol. Treatment of acid with thionyl chloride for 4 h provided the acid chloride in very good yield⁴⁵. The reaction of with various imines in dichloromethane in the presence of triethylamine using microwave irradiation provided the TCP-protected α -amino- β -lactams in moderate yields with varying *cis/trans* ratio. Acid chloride reacted with imine in chlorobenzene in the presence of N-methylmorpholine under microwave irradiation for 3–5 min, and provided TCP-protected β -

lactams in excellent yield. *Trans*-selectivity was observed (more than 90%) when the reaction was performed under microwave irradiation. Under conventional conditions, however, the product was a mixture of *cis/trans*-isomers in varying proportions. This reaction was selective since no cleavage of the β -lactam ring was observed. Interestingly, in the case of 4-styryl-2-azetidinone only the *cis*- β -lactam was the product obtained by this method. This was the product even under a high level of microwave irradiation. In another method, the imines were prepared by a general method. This was performed by refluxing 2-amino thiazole with different aromatic aldehydes. On cyclocondensation of imines with phenyl acetyl chloride and in the presence of triethylamine, azetidinones as shown in was afforded in 60–65% yields. The ^1H NMR showed a *cis*-configuration of the C-3 and C-4 protons of the 2-azetidinone ring. Each proton at C-3 and C-4 showed as a doublet. Polarization of the molecules under microwave irradiation caused rapid reaction to occur. Importantly, the yields were high (85–95%) under microwave irradiation conditions. Using conventional heating however, the yields were comparatively low (60–65%). The negative charges of the oxygen and nitrogen atoms of 1,3-thiazolyl group as well as the partial pi positive charges of sulfur and supplementary arm 2-OH contributed in favor of an antibacterial activity. Additionally it was established that the activity is improved with increase in negative charge of one heteroatom of the pharmacophore fragment of the compounds⁴⁶. A systematic study to address the use of microwave techniques in the synthesis of β -lactam rings from 1,3-azadienes in the absence of solvents, following a two-step Staudinger reaction was performed. The starting azadiene was prepared from a silylimine. The silylimine was in turn obtained from an aldehyde and an acyl chloride. The N-trialkylsilyl-substituted azadienes was prepared with the hydrolytically stable TBDMS-group. According to the procedure the required N-*tert*-butyldimethylsilyl imine was prepared from lithium N,N-(*tert*butyldimethyl) trimethylsilyl amide and an aldehyde. Azadienes resulting from *tert*-butyldimethylsilylimines could be stored at low temperature to prepare β -lactam⁴⁷. A new procedure for the synthesis of β -aminoesters and β -lactams starting from imines and silyl ketene acetals was developed. Reaction of benzylidene aniline with the silyl ketene acetal over montmorillonite K10 afforded the β -aminoester⁴⁸.

Formation of β -lactams with polyaromatic imines

The stereochemistry of resulting β -lactams varies, including *cis*, *trans*, and a *cis-trans* mixture, depending on the substituents present in the imine and acid chloride and con. However, the reaction of polyaromatic imines with acetoxy, phenoxy, and phthalimido acid chloride in the presence of triethylamine at -78°C to room temperature produced *trans*- β -lactams. There was no report in the literature regarding the use of tetracyclic or pentacyclic aromatic systems in β -lactam formation was not described in the literature⁴⁹. Some previous studies were performed toward the formation of *trans*- β -lactams. The above concept has been extended to similar polyaromatic imines. As a model study, reaction of diarylimine with O-acetylmandelic chloride in the presence of triethylamine was performed at 0°C -room temperature and a single β -lactam was obtained in 70% yield. The acetate and the C-4 hydrogen in resonate at δ 1.6 and δ 5.7 respectively. Microwave-induced method, however, produced a mixture of two β -lactams in a ratio of 1 : 1 (70% yield). The acetate and the C-4 hydrogen in β -lactam resonate at δ 2.2 and δ 5.67 respectively. Cycloaddition of imine derived from a multicyclic aromatic amine at 0°C -room temperature afforded two products in a ratio of 7 : 3. Microwave irradiation, however, produced a mixture of two products in a ratio of 2 : 8. The acetate and C-4 hydrogen in resonate at δ 2.17 and δ 5.95 respectively. The acetate and C-4 hydrogen in resonate at δ 2.33 and 6.46 respectively. When irradiated in a microwave oven using chlorobenzene and triethylamine, β -lactam did not isomerize. The β -lactams also did not produce to isomeric β -lactams when they were refluxed in ethylenedichloride and triethylamine. These experiments established that there were no isomerization of the β -lactams during reaction at a high temperature and/or under microwave irradiation. This results in a *trans*- β -lactam in which C-4 phenyl and C-3 acetoxy groups are *trans* to each other in the predominant product. The classical condition using imine followed the normal cycloaddition path as reported in the literature and this gave *cis*-type of compounds (C-3 acetoxy and C-4 H are *trans* to each other). However, drastic energy through microwave radiation altered the structure of the intermediate presumably through a rotation of the bond and these results in the formation of different stereoisomers in major propor-

tion. Reaction of ferrocene aldehyde with 6-aminochrysene in toluene produced imine after 72 h reflux using a Dean-Stark water separator. The imine was then reacted with acid chloride at 0 °C-room temperature and a single *trans*- β -lactam was obtained in 70% yield. This result suggests that ferrocene group exerts a similar behavior like aromatic aldehydes in the Staudinger reaction.

The formation of a *trans*-isomer as observed in the present study can be rationalized through isomerization of the enolates. The electron withdrawing polyaromatic system at the nitrogen stabilizes the iminium ion⁵⁰. This process allows rotation of the bond and results in the formation of *trans*- β -lactam. This observation is similar to that described by Just *et al.*, in which formation of a *trans*-isomer having electron-withdrawing nitro-substituted imines was performed⁵¹. In contrast, the exclusive formation of a *cis*- β -lactam having a polyaromatic group and cinnamyl at C-4 prompted us to develop a hypothesis regarding a mechanism previously described by Doyle *et al.*⁵². In this context, extended conjugation of the cinnamyl and polyaromatic system stabilizes the acyliminium ion. Furthermore, the presence of the cinnamyl or polyaromatic system at C-4 outweighs the contribution of the N-polyaromatic system, resulting in *cis*- β -lactam formation. Subsequent proton abstraction from complex produced *cis*- β -lactam through (90° bond rotation and closure) or (anion inversion and closure). This hypothesis was further strengthened by the possible formation of donor-acceptor complex as suggested by Bose *et al.*⁵³. This complex formation effectively stabilized the transition states of the reaction.

Mechanism of β -lactam formation reactions

Georg and Ravikumar have established some general rules regarding stereoselectivity in the formation of β -lactam rings⁵³. Also, computer-assisted theoretical calculations have been advanced to explain the stereochemical outcome. Cossio and co-workers and Sordo and co-workers have explained the stereochemical results on the basis of torquoelectronic effects^{54,55}. Low-temperature infrared spectroscopy has been used by Lynch *et al.* to identify the reactive intermediates⁵⁶. In general, two mechanisms have been proposed to explain the product distribution in the β -lactam formation reaction. One of these, the ketene mechanism, was observed in a low-temperature infrared

spectroscopy study while the other, the acylation of imine mechanism was also believed to be involved. Both mechanisms were supported by numerous lines of evidence in several studies. In particular, it has been hypothesized that cycloaddition of the imine occurs from the least hindered side of the hetene, a process that generates zwitterionic intermediates; conrotatory cyclization of these intermediates can then provide *cis*- and *trans*- β -lactams. In addition, the latter mechanism proposes acylation of the imine by the acid chloride to form N-acyliminium chloride, which produces zwitterionic intermediates. Our current thoughts regarding the likely mechanisms by which this cycloaddition with polyaromatic imines proceeded are described below. Infra-red spectra had shown a strong band at 2200 cm^{-1} when acid chloride and imine were reacted in the presence of triethylamine within 30 min after the start of the reaction. This band mostly disappeared after 24 h or reaction. Therefore, a ketene was involved in this reaction as an intermediate. However, Cossio *et al.* described that the $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ intramolecular mechanism favored the preferential or exclusive formation of *trans*- β -lactams, particularly when the reactions were allowed to take place in the absence of a tertiary base in the initial stages of the reaction. In contrast, triethylamine was used as one of the reactants at the beginning of our experiment, yet the product was a *trans*- β -lactam in many cases as described here. The use of diisopropylethyl amine as the base did not improve the yield of the products. However, the stereochemistry of the products with polyaromatic imines remained identical. The stereoselectivity of *trans*- β -lactam can be explained on the basis of steric effects. It is postulated the isomerization of C=N bond prior to ring closure as a result of severe steric interactions. Undoubtedly, this mechanism explained our *trans*-selectivity, but did not explain *cis*-selectivity with similar types of compounds. Formation of a mixture of *cis*- and *trans*-isomers with naphthalenyl and anthracenyl imines could not be explained using the mechanisms described above. If the electron withdraw properties or the steric crowding of the N-polyaromatic system were solely responsible for the *trans*- β -lactam formation, then an identical stereochemical distribution would have been observed in the isomeric naphthalenyl and anthracenyl compounds. Comparison of these results and examination of the N-polyaromatic systems with which

trans-isomers were the only products revealed a structural similarity. These imines have a *peri* hydrogen very close to the C=N bond, whereas this *peri* hydrogen is relatively distant from the same bond in similar structures. But, it has been established that microwave irradiation can alter the stereochemical distribution when naphthalenyl and anthracenyl imines were used irrespective of the absence of the *peri* hydrogen. In contrast, several other imines with extended conjugation never produced *trans*- β -lactams even after performing the reactions under forcing conditions. In this respect, it appeared that stabilization of the positive charge by the extended conjugation is the major contributor in dictating the stereochemistry of the final β -lactams. These extensive results also indicate that it is the nature of the C-4 group that controls the isomer distribution in this type of reaction. The products as described in were obtained based on hypothesis-driven work on conformationally restricted compounds⁵⁴.

Synthesis of diverse β -lactams

Polycyclic novel β -lactams were prepared starting from cyclic imine through microwave irradiation as shown in⁵⁵. It has been found that clay can help to form imine and Staudinger reaction can be performed with success in a one-pot operation⁵⁶.

Rearrangement of the β -lactam ring

Pyrohidines and oxazines were prepared from β -lactam rearrangement reaction using domestic microwave oven very easily. For example, *trans*- β -lactam on treatment with sodium methoxide in methanol produced pyrrolidine via the cleavage and subsequent rearrangement⁵⁷. This reaction proceeded equally well with *cis*- β -lactams. Oxazines were derived under reductive conditions with indium-metal induced reactions of the nitro group. The nitro group was reduced to amino group. It was difficult to isolate the amino compound. The close proximity of the amino group and the 4-membered ring was suitable for a molecular rearrangement. On nucleophilic attack by the amino group to the β -lactam carbonyl group, the ring was cleaved and oxazines were formed in good yield⁵⁸. This reaction was possible with optically active substrates with acid-sensitive groups. The resulting oxazines were highly functionalized and therefore were well-suited for the construction of polycyclic oxazines.

Preparation of taxol and taxotere side chains

The formation of a single glycoside from optically active α -hydroxy β -lactams studied raised the possibility of synthesizing both enantiomeric forms of racemic β -lactams. On this basis, glycosylation of racemic *cis*-1-(*p*-anisyl)-3-hydroxy-4-phenyl-2-azetidinone was investigated in detail. On treatment with glucal triacetate and iodine in tetrahydrofuran solution, led in 60% yield to a mixture of two diastereomeric compounds in the ratio of 55 : 45. Catalyst transfer hydrogenation of in ethanol produced a 2,3,4-trideoxyglucoside. The catalytic transfer hydrogenation reaction using a domestic microwave oven in ethylene glycol produced an identical product within 2 min. The small couplings for the anomeric proton indicated that a α -glycosidic linkage had been formed. This reaction was performed by placing the reaction mixture in a large beaker or an Erlenmeyer flask with a loose cover for a top and a beaker of water by its side. Irradiation for 2 min under low energy setting heated the reaction mixture to about 80 °C. The diastereomers were separated through column chromatography and treated individually with aqueous hydrochloric acid solution or bismuth nitrate-catalyzed reaction to remove the sugar moiety. As expected, the hydroxy β -lactams were obtained and these were then converted to their corresponding acetates in 90% yield. Although aqueous hydrochloride acid worked well in the cleavage of the hemiacetal bond in, we discovered that an aqueous solution of bismuth nitrate produced products in comparable yields.

2-Fluoro-3-formyl substituted quinolines gave the corresponding hydrazones upon reduction with ocranoid acid hydrazide in ethanol. β -Lactams is afforded through conventional heating and by reaction with chloroacetyl chloride and triethylamine in a microwave oven⁴³. Reaction pathway is also depicted in. Domestic and automated microwave-induced reactions are explored systematically with different other substrates. Most of the instances, there is a tendency to form *trans*- β -lactams. The synthesis of *trans*-isomer was investigated using related methods⁶⁰. The mechanism of *trans*- β -lactam formation was also explained in some elegant studies⁶¹. Higher activation energy transformations that are difficult and impossible to complete with conventional heating (oil bath, steam bath, and mantle) can be performed very easily with microwave irradiation because of the facile energy transfer pro-

cess. Heat is applied externally and it passes through the walls of the reaction vessel and solvent during thermally-assisted chemical reactions. Therefore, some of the reactions under thermal conditions may not prove efficient. However, microwave-induced reactions have a number of advantages because of microwave-coupling, microwave heating, microwave irradiation and molecular heating. Microwave coupling is the direct transfer of microwave energy to a substrate that results in instantaneous heating. Microwave heating is the direct energy transfer process to the reaction mixtures; this raises kinetic excitation and is characterized by rapid energy transfer. Microwave irradiation is a form of non-ionizing radiation that transfers energy by interacting with polar molecules. In addition, the direct energy transfer from microwave to the molecules will greatly enhance the speed of the chemical reaction (solventless reaction). Therefore, microwave-induced reactions will continue to attract chemists and industrialists for the synthesis of novel molecules with controlled stereochemistry, higher yield and because of the green nature of the process.

Conclusion

We have demonstrated facile stereoselective synthesis of a number of new anticancer active β -lactams starting from polyaromatic imines. The β -lactam derivatives described herein are novel, and they demonstrate reasonable *in vitro* antitumor cytotoxicity. Carbohydrates are used to induce asymmetry in the synthesis of anticancer β -lactams in both enantiomeric forms. The stereochemical outcome of the Staudinger reaction as reported herein is unprecedented. These results offer our laboratory and other many additional opportunities to use β -lactams in the synthesis of biologically active compounds³⁹. A number of mechanisms are discussed to explain the origin of the stereochemical distribution of the products. Although the mechanism of action of the lead anticancer compounds has not been totally established, our research on cell cycle analysis offers intriguing possibilities. In the absence of effect upon DNA or DNA enzyme-systems they produced a striking blockade. This "check point" in the cell cycle has attracted a considerable amount of attention recently. Studies are now in progress to determine the exact site of this action and to utilize it in an effort to modify our β -lactams to obtain more potent compounds. It is our ex-

pectation that novel anticancer β -lactams with high potency and unique mechanism of action will be discovered by other researchers as well. Moreover, several reactions are performed on β -lactams for the preparation of racemic and optically active organic molecules of current interests. Microwave-induced reactions have been proved to be crucial in the preparation of many β -lactams and products derived from them.

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